

**EFFECT OF TEAM TEACHING METHOD ON STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN
BRICK/BLOCKLAYING AND CONCRETING IN TECHNICAL COLLEGES OF GOMBE
STATE**

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Abstract

This study determined the effects of Team Teaching Method on students' academic performance in brick/blocklaying and concreting trade in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Gombe state Nigeria. The study was guided by four purposes with their corresponding three research questions and three null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of alpha. The study was carried out in Gombe state. The population of the study was made up of 304 students while 60 NTC II BBC students formed the sample for the study. Three sampling techniques were used for the study. The subjects were separated into two groups; the experimental group I (N = 28) and the control group (N=32) using intact classes. The study adopted pretest, posttest nonequivalent quasi-experimental and control group design. The topics taught were foundation of building construction and bonding concepts and skills. The instrument for data collection was Brick/Blocklaying and Concreting Performance Test (BBCPT) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by expert and tested for reliability which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.87. The three research questions were answered and three hypotheses were tested. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariates (ANCOVA) at 0.05 alpha level. The findings shows that; there was significant difference in the performance of students taught brick/blocklaying and concreting using team and demonstration teaching methods $F, (df=1, 60) = 14.076, p = 0.023$, there was significant difference between males and females brick/blocklaying and concreting students' performance $F, (df=1, 60) = 14.076, p > 0.05$ less 0.023, there was no interaction effect of the teaching methods and gender on students' performance $F (df=1, 60) = 14.076, p > 0.05$, thus the computed p-value (0.008) is greater than 0.05 level of significant. The study recommended among others that teachers should be encouraged to use Team teaching method in technical colleges. On-the-job training for BBC teachers in form of seminars, workshops and conferences should be organized on how to use team teaching method in teaching brick/blocklaying and concreting trade.

Keywords: Team Teaching, brick/blocklaying and concreting, students' performance

Introduction

Technical colleges are the formal institutions where vocational and technical courses are offered by students for acquiring knowledge, skills and attitudes. According to Tsado (2013) technical colleges are aimed at giving training and imparting the necessary skills in various occupations such as auto mechanics, plumbing, carpentry and joinery, cabinet making, painting and decorating, welding, electrical installation, radio, and television repairs and

brick/blocklaying and concreting leading to the production of craftsmen, technicians and other skilled personnel who will be enterprising and self-reliant among others. Brick/block laying and concreting trade is among the trades that offer students the skills necessary for enterprising in construction industries.

According to Sikemi (2013), brick/blocklaying and concreting trade (BBCT) is that aspect of technical and vocational education that is meant to equip students with technical knowledge and vocational skills that will make the trainees enterprise or become self-reliant. The brick/blocklaying and concreting work and practices can only be achieved through teaching and learning by the teacher using activity-based methods such as inquiry, project, and Team Teaching Method.

Team teaching is a group of two or more teachers working together to plan, conduct and evaluate the learning activities for the same group of learners. Wang (2010) defined team teaching as "simply teamwork between two qualified instructors who, together, make a presentation to an audience." Wang (2010) noted that team teaching efforts "include two or more faculty in some level of collaboration in the planning and delivery of a course." Team teaching implies two broad categories: one is that two or more instructors are teaching the same students at the same time within the same classroom. This implies that each speaks freely during large-group instruction and moves among all the students in the class.; the other is that the instructors work together but do not necessarily teach the same groups of students nor necessarily teach at the same time.

According to Nkechi, Lilian-Rita and Ngozi (2015), Team Teaching Method (TTM) is different from Single Teacher Teaching Method (STTM) because it involves two or more teachers each with distinctive roles, sharing responsibilities for planning, presentation and evaluation of lessons for the same group of students. Nkechi, Lilian-Rita and Ngozi (2015) also viewed team teaching as two or more teachers who combine their talents, expertise, interests and resources to take joint responsibility for any or all aspects of teaching the same students According to Brandenbury in Nkechi, Lilian-Rita and Ngozi (2015) team teaching exposes students to a variety of teaching styles and approaches, which increases the potential for the team to meet the various learning styles of students. However, while team teaching may prove advantageous for many students, some may feel frustration and discontentment about having more than one teacher. But with proper collaboration and cohesiveness within a team, there are vital benefits for those willing to adopt a team-teaching approach.

Aliakbari and Mansouri (2013) view team teaching as follows: "two teachers are jointly responsible for a class and plan to teach together, plan instruction together, share teaching duties and design collectively all teaching aids". Additionally, Aliakbari and Mansouri (2013) note that team teaching in the early 1970s was known as team teaching, and it was also known as collaborative teaching, or cooperative teaching.

Aliakbari and Mansouri (2013) rightly noted that such terms refer to a context where two or three teachers share some responsibility in teaching the same group of students have different implications in terms of pedagogical concerns. Team teaching has the contributions of each participant in focus. Team teaching known also as collaborative and cooperative teaching is a general term referring to the pedagogical setting where two teachers share their pedagogy, information, and assessment while team teaching is considered as one of the distinct instructional models of the team teaching framework. Team teaching is subject to "teaching styles, learning philosophies, interpersonal skills, shared experiences, and licensure status".

In a different description, Cook and Friend in Aliakbari and Mansouri (2013) argued that a team teaching system has two or more teachers to mutually convey "substantive instruction" to a heterogeneous group of pupils in one class. In other words, a team-teaching system has been established on highly substantial teaching methods and features that distinguish it from such a traditional interpretation.

Demonstration teaching method involves illustrating a point in a lecture or a lesson employing something other than routine visual aids or other means of instruction. A demonstration in chemistry may be defined as a pedagogical event whose objective is to illustrate a scientific concept (Ahmad, Muhammad, Naji, & Avi (2017). According Ahmad, Muhamad, Naji, and Avi (2017) stated that a well prepared and properly presented demonstration method has the potential to enhance students' understanding of concepts. Similarly, Hofstein and Lunettain Ahmad, Muhammad, Naji and Avi (2017) in their comprehensive reviews, concluded that demonstration method has the potential to enhance learning, motivation, and attitude. Some teaching methods used in teaching technical trade may have a significant effect on gender performance (males and females).

Gender refers to feminine or masculine which also means males and females brick/block laying and concreting students in technical colleges. Ibrahim, Adisa, Abdulkadir and Nene (2013) defined gender as the result of socially constructed ideas about the behaviours, actions and roles a particular sex performs. There is a societal feeling that technical skills are only suitable for the males and the females' counterparts are discriminated against and discouraged from such type of career. Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) also stated gender is a psychological experience of being a male or female. It has to do with personality and central components of self-concept. Unlike sex, which is concerned with, only the distinction between males and females based on biological characteristics. Gender encompasses other personality attributes as roles, orientation and identity based on an individual's conceptualization of self. For instance, Singh (2010) opined that gender refers to a socio-cultural construct that connotes the differentiated roles and responsibilities of men and women in a particular society.

Gender is a specially constructed phenomenon that is brought about as society ascribes different roles, duties, behaviours, and mannerisms to the two sexes (Nnamani & Oyibe, 2016). It is a social connotation that has a sound psychological background, and it is used to refer to specific cultural patterns of behaviour that are attributed to the human sexes. Gender relates to the cultural attributes of both males and females Nnamani&Oyibe, (2016). Gender according to Laheyin Nnamaniand Oyibe (2016) is a psychological experience of being a male or female. It has to do with personality and central components of self-concept. Unlike sex, which is concerned with, only the distinction between males and females based on biological characteristics, gender encompasses other personality attributes as roles, orientation and identity based on an individual's conceptualization of self. For instance, Singh (2010) opines that gender refers to a socio-cultural construct that connotes the differentiated roles and responsibilities of men and women in a particular society. This definition implies that gender determines the role, which one plays concerning the general political, cultural, social, and economic system of the society. According to Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) gender refers to all the characteristics of males and females, in which a particular society has determined and assigned each sex. Also, Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) sees gender as the dichotomy of roles culturally imposed on the sexes.

Tafida et al. (2019) stated that there is a negative societal perception that technical and vocational skills acquisition is incompatible with the mother's role, at home and that girls who take to such careers have small chances

to get married. These negative thoughts may influence the interest and self-confidence of the female folk and reduce their ability and motivation to opt for careers in technical skills acquisition. Eze et al. (2015) observed that there is a general belief that boys are superior to girls in terms of cognition and logical reasoning and even in academic performance.

Students' academic performance is the extent to which the students' learners achieved the desired goals and objectives in a learning environment. As students remain the most important assets for every educational institution, so also the social and economic development of the country is directly linked with the students' academic performance. The academic performance of the students plays an important role in producing competent graduates who will become great leaders and manpower for the country thus responsible for the country's socioeconomics development (Mushtaq & Nawaz, 2012).

Jane (2014) stated that Academic performance is the quality and quantity of knowledge, skills, techniques and positive attitudes, behaviour and philosophy that students achieve or acquire. This achievement is evaluated by the mark or grade that students attain in a term education cycle. The quality of grades and the number of students that pass in the various grades determine the level of academic performance. There are many factors, which account for the good or poor academic performance in technical colleges like; the quality of students admitted the type of scholastic materials available in the school and home environment, the methods of teaching, the nature of administration and teacher involvement in academic matters.

Statement of the Problem

The declined in academic performance reported by Eze, et al., (2015) among others of students in technical subjects in Nigerian technical colleges is a great concern to vocational educators because of the relevance of technical education to individual self-reliance and the nation's technological and industrial development. Research studies have strongly related the academic performance of students to the methods of teaching employed by the teachers (Adunola, 2011 & Ganyaupfu, 2013).

The common teaching method used by teachers in the delivery of technical subjects is uncalled-for which is often generates frustration and learning hitches for students. Diraso, et al., (2015) reported that information received from FCE (T) Gombe revealed that, about 86% of the students admitted into the NCE (Technical) programme had attended technical colleges in Gombe State. Yet the academic performance of technical colleges in Gombe state is poor t. This may not be unconnected with the teachers' competencies, teachers' methods of teaching, the inadequacy of training material, policy implementation, over the crowd of students in the classroom to mention among others.

Therefore, to address the issue of students' academic performance in technical colleges has become necessary because it will affect the development of the state and the nation at large. It is against this background that the researcher carried out the study on the effects of Team teaching method on brick/block laying and concreting students' performance in technical colleges in Gombe State with a view to a proper solution to the existing problem.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the effects of Team teaching method on Brick/ Blocklaying and Concreting students' performance in technical colleges in Gombe State. Specifically, the study:

1. Determine the mean scores of BBC students taught using Team teaching method and those taught using demonstration teaching method in Government technical colleges in Gombe state
2. Determine the mean scores of males and females brick/blocklaying and concreting students taught using the Team teaching method in technical colleges in Gombe state
3. Determine the mean scores of males and females brick/blocklaying and concreting students using demonstration teaching method in technical colleges in Gombe state
4. determine the interaction effect of teaching methods and gender

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised in line with the objectives to guide the study:

1. What are the mean scores of BBC students taught using Team and demonstration teaching methods in Government technical colleges in Gombe state
2. What are the mean scores of males and females BBC students taught using the Team teaching method in technical colleges in Gombe state
3. What are the mean scores of males and females BBC students taught using demonstration method of teaching in technical colleges in Gombe state

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁ There is no significant difference in the performance of BBC students taught using Team and demonstration teaching methods

HO₂ There is no significant difference in the performance of males and females BBC students taught using Team and demonstration teaching methods

HO₃ There is no interaction effect of teaching methods and gender

Methodology

The study adopted pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental research design. Quasi-experimental design investigates possible cause and effect as well as relationship between two or more variables by the application of treatment which cannot be resolved by mere description or observation. The area of the study is in Gombe state which is located between longitude 10⁰E15⁰N and latitude 12⁰E 11⁰N. The target population for the study was three hundred and four (304) NTCII BBC students of Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe state. There are 7 technical colleges in Gombe state namely GSTC Barunde, GSTC Kumo, GSTC Amada, GSTC Deba, GSTC Kwami, GSTC Gombe and GSTC Tula. Purposive sampling technique was used to select three core-educational technical colleges. These included Government Science and Technical College Kwami, Government Science Technical College Barunde and Government Science and Technical College (GSTC) Tula. The sample for the study was made up of 60 NTC II BBC students using intact classes. The instrument for data collection was Brick/blocklaying and Concreting Achievement Test BBCAT. The achievement Test contained 50 multiple-choice items that were adopted from NABTEB past questions from 2014 to 2020. The Fifty (50) items

(BBCTAT) were constructed based on topics covered as contained in the NTCII BBCT scheme of work. The main topic deals with “brick/block bonding and foundation in building construction.

The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Technology Education MAU Yola and one from the Department of Technical Education FCET Gombe. The experts scrutinized the instrument in terms of face and contents validity. The instrument was trial tested in Government Science and Technical College Yola using NTC II BBC students which is not part of the researcher study area. The result obtained from the trial test was analysed using the crown Bach formular and a reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained.

The researcher collected the data for the study through the following procedure: The pre-test was administered prior to the commencement of the treatment to determine their academic ability level before the treatment, while the post-test was administered after the treatment. The experimental group was exposed to 6 weeks treatment using the Team teaching method while the control group was exposed to the same 6 weeks using demonstration teaching method (conventional method). The post test was conducted on both groups of students at the end of the training session. The data collected was analysed using mean and standard deviation in answering the research questions while analysis of covariate was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Decision taking for testing the null hypotheses was based on comparing the computed p-value with the level of significance. Where the computed p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was accepted and concluded that, there was no significant difference among the variables compared while on the other hand if the computed p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected and concluded that, there was significant difference among the variables compared.

Results

The results of the study were presented in tabular form based on the research Questions and hypotheses

Research Question 1. What are the mean scores of BBC students taught using Team and demonstration teaching methods in Government technical colleges of Gombe state?

Table 1: Mean scores of BBC Students Taught Using Team and Demonstration Teaching Method

Teaching Methods	Pre test		Post Test		
	N	\bar{X}	S.D	\bar{X}	S.D
Team Teaching Method	28	4.10	2.02	32.10	9.50
Demonstration Teaching Method	32	4.07	1.63	17.96	5.85
Mean Difference		0.03	0.39	14.14	0.65

The result in Table 1: reveals the pre-test mean difference in BBC students taught using Team teaching method as 0.03 with a correspondent standard deviation of 0.39 and a post-test mean difference of 14.14 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.65. The margin lead mean score between the team teaching method and the demonstration method during the post-test was 14.14 in favour of team teaching method against the demonstration teaching method. This shows that team teaching method improves BBC students than demonstration teaching method.

Research Question 2. What are the mean scores of males and females Brick/ Blocklaying and Concreting students taught using Team teaching method in technical colleges in Gombe state?

Table2: Mean difference of Males and females BBC Students Taught Using Team Teaching Method.

Team Teaching Method	Pre test			Post Test	
	N	\bar{X}	S.D	\bar{X}	S.D
Male	20	4.14	1.86	35.68	14.67
Female	8	4.00	0.76	22.25	3.96
Mean Difference		0.14	1.10	13.43	10.71

The result in Table 2 reveals the pre-test mean difference of males and females BBC students was 0.14 with a corresponding standard deviation of 1.10 and a post-test mean difference of 13.43 with a corresponding standard deviation of 10.71. The margin lead mean score between males and females BBC students was 13.43 in favour of males against females. This shows that males BBC students had better improvement than female BBC students taught using team teaching method.

Research Question 3. What are the mean scores of males and females Brick/blocklaying and Concreting students taught using demonstration teaching method in technical colleges of Gombe state?

Table 3: Mean scores of Males and Females BBC Students Taught Using Demonstration Teaching Method.

Demonstration Method	Pre test			Post Test	
	N	\bar{X}	S.D	\bar{X}	S.D
Males	25	4.24	2.15	17.96	6.37
Females	7	3.20	0.84	18.00	2.00
Mean Difference		1.04	1.31	-0.04	4.37

The information in Table 3 reveals the pre-test mean difference between males and females BBC students taught using demonstration teaching method as 1.04 with a corresponding standard deviation of 1.31 and a post-test mean difference of - 0.04 with a corresponding standard deviation of 4.37. The margin lead mean score between the males and female BBC students is -0.04 in favour of females against the males BBC students. This shows that females BBC students had fairly improved than their male counterparts taught using demonstration teaching method.

Hypothesis 1

HO₁: There was no significant difference in the mean performance of Brick/blocklaying and Concreting students taught using Team and demonstration teaching methods

Table 4: One way Analysis of Covariate among Team and Demonstration Teaching Methods on BBC students' Performance.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	5905.916 ^a	6	984.319	15.249	.000
Intercept	4402.827	1	4402.827	68.206	.000
PRETST	239.099	1	239.099	3.704	.057
TEAHMETS	1817.216	1	908.608	14.076	.000
Error	6132.397	95	64.552		
Total	60182.000	60			
Corrected Total	12038.314	59			

a. R Squared = .491 (Adjusted R Squared = .458)

The result in table 4 presented the one way Analysis of Covariate between Team and Demonstration Teaching Methods on BBC student performance. The F, (1, 60) = 14.076, p- value = 0.00 tested at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the computed probability value is less 0.05 level of precision, hence, the null hypothesis was rejected indicating that there was significant difference among the performance of BBC students taught using Team and Demonstration Teaching Methods. Therefore, multiple comparisons analysis was run to precisely identify the teaching method that was responsible for the difference.

Table 5: Bonferonni Multiple Comparisons Post Hoc Analysis between Team Teaching and Demonstration Teaching Methods

(I) Teaching Methods	(J) Teaching Methods	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Team Teaching Method	Demonstration Teaching Method	10.631*	2.580	.000	4.343	16.920
Demonstration Teaching Method	Team Teaching Method	-10.631*	2.580	.000	-16.920	-4.343

Table 5 shows the results of Bonferroni Multiple Comparisons Analysis between Team and Demonstration Teaching Methods. The result indicates that team teaching method compared with demonstration teaching method a mean difference of 10.631* was obtained with a p-value 0.00 indicating that there is a significant difference between team teaching and demonstration teaching method in favour of team teaching method against demonstration teaching method.

Hypothesis 2

HO₂ There is no significant difference in the mean performance of males and females Bricklaying, Blocklaying and Concreting students taught using Team and demonstration teaching methods.

Table 6: One way Analysis of Covariate between the Performance of Males and Females BBC Students Taught Using Team Teaching and Demonstration Teaching Methods

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	5905.916 ^a	6	984.319	15.249	.000
Intercept	4402.827	1	4402.827	68.206	.000
PRETST	239.099	1	239.099	3.704	.057
GENDER	344.881	1	344.881	5.343	.023
Error	6132.397	54	64.552		
Total	60182.000	60			
Corrected Total	12038.314	59			

a. R Squared = .491 (Adjusted R Squared = .458)

The result in Table 12 presented the one way Analysis of Covariate between males and females BBC students performance taught using Team Teaching and Demonstration Teaching Methods on BBC in Government Science and Technical colleges in Gombe State. The F, (1, 60) = 5.343, p- value = 0.023 tested at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the computed probability value is less 0.05 level of significant, hence, the null hypothesis was rejected indicating that there was significant difference among the performance of males and females BBC students taught using Team Teaching and Demonstration Teaching Methods. Therefore, multiple comparisons analysis was run to precisely identify the group that is responsible for the significant difference.

Table 7: Bonferonni Multiple Comparisons Post Hoc Analysis between Males and females BBC Students Taught Using Team Teaching, Team Teaching and Demonstration Teaching Methods

(I) Males and females	(J) Males and females	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	Female	4.548*	1.968	.023	.642	8.455
Female	Male	-4.548*	1.968	.023	-8.455	-.642

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

The result in Table 7 showed that the Male BBC students' performance were compared with their counterpart Female and indicated a significant difference of 0.023 with a mean difference of 4.548* in favour of male.

Hypothesis 3

HO₃ There was no interaction effect of teaching methods and gender

Table 8: One-Way Analysis of Covariate on the Interaction Effects of Teaching Methods and Gender.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	5905.916 ^a	6	984.319	15.249	.000
Intercept	4402.827	1	4402.827	68.206	.000
PRETST	239.099	1	239.099	3.704	.057
TEAHMETS * GENDER	657.463	1	328.731	5.093	.008
Error	6132.397	54	64.552		
Total	60182.000	60			
Corrected Total	12038.314	59			

a. R Squared = .491 (Adjusted R Squared = .458)

The result in Table 8 presented the one way Analysis of Covariate on the interaction effects of teaching methods and gender, $F(1, 60) = 5.093$, $p\text{-value} = 0.008$ tested at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the computed probability value is greater than 0.05 level of alpha; hence, the null hypothesis was accepted indicating that there was no interaction effect of teaching methods on gender

Findings of the Study

The following findings were revealed base on the research questions and hypotheses:

1. The Team Teaching Method had a higher mean compared to demonstration teaching method with a post-test mean difference of 14.14.
2. The post-test mean difference between males and females BBC students' taught using team teaching is 13.43 in favour of males against females.
3. The post-test mean difference between males and females BBC students taught using demonstration method was - 0.04 is in favour of female against the males BBC students.
4. There was significant difference among the performance of BBC students taught using Team and Demonstration Teaching Methods with a probability value of 0.00.
5. There was significant difference among the performance of males and females BBC students taught using Team Teaching and Demonstration Teaching Methods with a probability value 0.023 in favour of Male against female.
6. There was interaction effect of teaching methods of gender with a probability value of 0.008

Discussion of Findings

The finding in research question 1 revealed that Team Teaching Method had a higher than demonstration teaching methods with a post-test mean of 14.14. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Abrak (2015) who found out that students perform better in fine art when taught using the Team Teaching Method as compared to the conventional method. In addition Nkechi, *et al.*,(2015) found out similarly that, the students taught English language comprehension with the team teaching approach achieved significantly higher than those of the control group who were taught with a single teacher teaching approach. Akpan, *et al.*,(2010) found similarly that that Students taught

Introductory Technology through the team-teaching approach performed significantly better than students taught by a single instructor. However, the finding of Ochogba, *et al.*, (2019) contrasted with the present finding who found that students taught with the demonstration method did better than those taught with the lecture.

The finding in research question 2 reveals that the post-tests mean difference of between males and females BBC students taught using Team teaching method is 13.43 in favour of male against the females. This finding is in contrast with the finding of Abrak (2015) who found out that Female students are better in fine art performance when taught using the Team Method. However, this finding is not in agreement with the finding of Nkechi, *et al.*, (2015) who found that female students in the Team Teaching Approach group achieved significantly higher than their male counterparts.

The finding in research question 3 reveals that the post-test mean difference between males and females BBC students taught using demonstration method was - 0.04 in favour of female against the males BBC students. The finding of the hypothesis reveals that there was significant difference among the performance of BBC students taught using Team Teaching and Demonstration Teaching Methods with a probability value of 0.00. This study is in line with the finding of Ochogba, *et al.*, (2019) who found that there was a significant difference in the mean score of students taught with the demonstration method and those taught with the lecture method in the production of wood and metal. The finding of the hypothesis 2 reveals that there was significant difference among the performance of males and females BBC students taught using Team Teaching and Demonstration Teaching Methods with a probability value 0.023 in favour of Male against female. This finding is in contrast with the finding of Tafida, *et al.*, (2019) who found that there was no significant difference among the performance of males and females BBC students taught using inquiry and demonstration teaching methods. The finding of the hypothesis reveals that there was no interaction effect of teaching methods on gender with a probability value of 0.08. It is also in line with the finding of Tafida, *et al.*, (2019) who found out that there was no interaction effect of teaching methods on gender.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should emphasize on technical colleges teachers use of Team Teaching Method in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe state.
2. Government should organize workshop, seminars on the use of Team Teaching Method in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe state.
3. Government should provide the necessary facilities in the delivery of Team Teaching Method in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe state.

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